

AI-PRISM

**D4.4 – AI-PRISM
Human Robot
Cooperation
Ambient (IV)**

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
TDB	To Be Determined
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

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1. Introduction

OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

Deliverable D4.4 is a continuation and update of Deliverable D4.3, presenting the current status of components developed within Work Package 4 (WP4) as of reporting month M39. It outlines the progress in CI/CD infrastructure (code repositories, pipelines, and project scaffolds), as well as the latest releases of AI-based modules that enhance perception, reasoning, coordination, and learning from human demonstration in collaborative environments.

The main objectives of WP4 are:

- Design and validation of CI/CD pipelines for AI-PRISM solutions.
- Development of AI-based perception modules to improve ambient sensing.
- Development of AI-based reasoning modules for individual agents.
- Development of AI-based reasoning modules for multi-agent coordination.
- Implementation of programming-by-demonstration techniques to transfer human knowledge to robotic agents.

The most up-to-date documentation of AI-PRISM components is available online:

<https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/>

STATUS GUIDELINES

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested
On hold	Task temporary paused

2. Architecture of AI-enhancing tools

Deliverable D4.4 continues the definition of AI-PRISM components initiated in D3.3 and previously detailed in D4.3. No significant architectural changes have occurred since the last release; this document primarily updates the development status of WP4 components.

WP4 focuses on AI-enhancing tools that improve the perception and reasoning capabilities of collaborative robots. These include:

- The CI/CD Framework for AI-based solutions, offering online services, templates, and runtime components to support development and deployment within the ROS-2 platform from WP3.
- Perception modules for tasks such as object and defect detection, pose estimation, speech recognition, and person tracking.
- Reasoning modules that utilize perception data to support agent control and coordination.
- Released components for Programming by Demonstration (PbD), enabling knowledge transfer from humans to robots.

The Reference Architecture and technical details remain available in the online documentation.

3.3. Modules

CI/CD FRAMEWORK FOR AI-BASED SOLUTIONS – CD (PIAP)

^{3.1.1.} The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4>

GITLAB TOOLING

Module name	GITLAB TOOLING			
General description	Gitlab tooling is the basis for our CI/CD. The infrastructure is located on independent servers at PIAP. It enables, among others: tracking tasks in the project, code repository, CI/CD pipelines and package and containers registry.			
Gitlab link	Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	-	This is the first functional GitLab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tooling. It includes issue tracking and container registry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduced issue tracking • First CI pipeline integration (frontend_template project) • Added default CI/CD runner • Enabled container registry • Gitlab updates • Extended storage space (>1TB) 	Completed
3.0	April 2025	Third tooling version. It includes more templating features and new component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reorganization of folders structure • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD • Generate helm templates for each component 	Completed

3.1.2.

FRONTEND TEMPLATE

Module name		FRONTEND TEMPLATE		
General description		Frontend template based on the project identity colours and theme with examples pages including useful components for the rest of project partners. It also provides general guidelines on how to use it and best practices.		
Gitlab link		NextJS frontend template available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/aiprism_frontend_template		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional frontend template for the project with NextJS framework. It includes the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First NextJS version with generic components • Integration of project theme and styles • First Dockerfile 	Completed

		project colours and some basic components in different pages.		
2.0	December 31 st 2023	This is the epic of the second version of the template. It includes an update of the look and feel of the template to bring it closer to the theme of the project, including specific components that partners will need. A first integration with Keycloak will be made for the login and jinja templating features will be added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New components added. • Bring the template closer to the theme of the project. • First integration with Keycloak login (different branch). • Continuous integration added. • Minor bugs fixed. • Jinja templating features delayed to next epic. 	Partially completed. ON-HOLD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keycloak integration Delayed to next epic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating ON-HOLD
3.0	March 31 st 2024	Third frontend version. It includes Jinja templating features and new status component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating features delayed from the previous epic. • Status management component. • Graph component. • Solved issues raised from partners. 	Completed
3.1.3 Final version	July 23 rd 2024	Final fronted version	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minor bugs fixed related to environment variables 	Completed

CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS

Module name	CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS
General description	The Cluster Management provides an optimized environment for deploying and managing containerized applications and Kubernetes. It automates the installation of Docker, a single-node cluster with K3s, Helm, and Rancher, simplifying cluster orchestration and management. This toolkit serves as a foundational platform for developers and administrators to efficiently manage and scale containerized workloads with ease.

Gitlab link		Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/cluster_management		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first version in which Rancher on Kubernetes is installed and configured manually on Kubernetes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software pre-installation: Docker, K3s and Helm. • Installation of Rancher on Kubernetes cluster. 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the second version. It includes the integration of installing all software into a shell script, along with the necessary configuration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service verification and installation automation. • Modifying the Kubernetes node for SSL certificate configuration. • Adding a new cluster of AI-PRISM CMT for application deployment. • Application catalogue in Rancher. • DNS deployment fixed with an alternative (cigip-dev branch). • Possibility to configure SSL certificates and secure access 	Completed
3.0 3.1.4.	April 2025	Final version of the script	Bug fixed and additional features identified during the integration	Completed

MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES

Module name	MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES
General description	Machine learning templates for easy integration.
Gitlab link	Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/ml-project-template

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	December 2023	This is the first version on templates	First generic ML template	Completed

ROS OVERLAY WORKSPACE HELM JOB TEMPLATE

Module name		ROS 2 OVERLAY WORKSPACE HELM JOB TEMPLATE		
General description		Helm template to install ROS 2 packages in a ROS 2 service running in an edge device using Helm jobs.		
Gitlab link		Project Template available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/job_install		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	September 2024	First version of ROS 2 overlay workspace template	Install ROS 2 packages in running ROS Framework service	Completed
2.0	April 2025	Final version	CI/CD stage to generate Helm charts automatically	Completed

3.2.

AI-BASED PERCEPTION ENHANCING MODULES – PE (FBK)

The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules>.

OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION (2D/3D)

Module name		OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION
General description		The “object and defect detection” module is designed to work in the VIGO pilot, among others. It detects objects and their positions, as well as defects in the semiconductor structure. Specifically, it consists of two components: the Defect Detection module, which enables the detection of defects on the chip using AI, and the Few-shot Key Point Detection module, which enables the detection of a selected chip fragment using AI.

Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here for Defect Detection: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/object_and_defect_detection Gitlab is available here for Few-shot Keypoint Detection: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/object_and_defect_detection/aiprism_deploy		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the first prototype of module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detects key points on the structure • Annotation tool implemented 	Completed
2.0	June-July 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tool. Some improvements of existing features.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add CI/CD tools for containerisation 	Completed
3.0	April 2025	Third tooling version.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD • Add defects detection (postponed) 	Completed

3.2.2.

OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION

Module name		OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION		
General description		This module performs model-based zero-shot object 6D pose estimation, determining the rotation and translation of an object within a scene. It takes as input the 3D point cloud representing the object and an RGBD image capturing a partial view of the scene and produces as output the object's rotation and translation transformations relative to the sensor's reference frame.		
Gitlab link		The Git repository is available at: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/6d_pose_estimation		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	March 31, 2024	First version of the code performing object 6D pose estimation without the need for task-specific training data.	Python implementation based on the PyTorch library	Completed
2.0	June 2024	Second version of the code containing also a ROS2 wrapper of the python code released in v1 and a Gazebo simulator.	Module demonstrator running in a controlled Lab environment containing a collaborative robotic arm spray painting a chair	Completed
3.0	December 2025	Final version of the code.	Module demonstrator running in the Andreu World pilot facility	Completed

PCB GRASPING POINT ESTIMATION

3.2.3.

Module name		PCB GRASPING POINT ESTIMATION		
General description		Detects PCB Boards and determines best grasping position. Detections and estimation are robust in different lighting conditions.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is not available yet/ Managed internally by the responsible partner.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of März 2024	Initial iterations with various detection and grasping point estimation algorithms. Base design of training and execution pipeline.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluating different techniques empirically for detection and grasping point estimation. Base version of training and execution pipeline. 	Completed
2.0	30 st of September 2024	Execution pipeline implementation done. Detection and grasping point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Object detection with Yolo8obb integrated Successfully used a small data set (64 	Completed

		estimation in different lighting conditions Implemented and verified through empirical testing.	images) for transfer learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detections robust regardless of lighting conditions • Grasping point estimation robust for densely packed PCBs • Grasping point estimation pipeline tested in laboratory environment 	
3.0	31 st March 2025	Implementation on Edge device KEBA PLC. ROS2 Wrappers developed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Execution pipeline implemented on KEBA PLC. • Inference on edge device CPU (considering kernel-related limitations) 	Completed
4.0	31 st May 2025	Training on the Shopfloor pipeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training pipeline can be triggered by operator via UI • Automated training data acquisition • Introduction of Novel PCB types 	Completed

3.2.4.

PCB POSE ESTIMATION

Module name	PCB POSE ESTIMATION			
General description	This module for PCB 6D-pose estimation—combining high-resolution 2D image registration with low-cost depth sensing—enables accurate and robust and precise PCB localization.			
Gitlab link	Gitlab is not available yet / Managed internally by the responsible partner. Documentation available here: https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/Components/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/PCB_detection/			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31st of March 2024	Initial Design of Ai-driven Image registration Pipeline.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ai-driven Image registration Pipeline. 	Completed
2.0	30st of September 2024	Successfully implemented AI-driven image registration. Conducted experiments utilizing various feature extractors and matching techniques to evaluate performance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented Pose Estimation Pipeline • conducted various Experiments for evaluation 	Completed
3.0	31st of March 2025	Integrated a two-stage approach to achieve both high accuracy and low latency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two-stage approach • High accuracy and low latency 	Completed
4.0	31st of May 2025	ROS2 Wrappers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixes 	Completed

3.2.5.

2D DEFECT DETECTION

Module name		2D DEFECT DETECTION		
General description		The 2D Defect detection module is designed to detect, analyse, and classify objects, defects, or patterns using advanced computer vision and AI techniques. This component has been specifically designed to provide improved accuracy, efficiency, and robustness in industrial settings and is deployed in SILVERLINE pilot		
Gitlab link		The link to the repository: 2D Defect Detection		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	June 2024	The initial release of the defect detection module with basic AI-based analysis and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-based object detection. • Image analysis for defects 	Completed

		detection capabilities.		
2.0	August 2024	The updated version with enhanced defect classification and more robust performance in industrial environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved accuracy • Additional defect categories, enhanced processing speed 	Completed
3.0	January 2025	Optimizing the system for real-time processing at scale and ensuring its seamless deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time functionality 	Completed

SPEECH RECOGNITION

3.2.6.

Module name		Speech Recognition		
General description		The Speech Recognition module is designed to recognize speech as part of seamless human-machine interaction.		
Gitlab link		The Git repository is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/speech-recognition		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Jan 2024	Demo with controlled audio recording of voice.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transcribe audio recording to text 	Completed
2.0	Feb 2025	Demo with automatic live recognition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic voice activity detection • Keyword detection 	Completed
3.0	May 2025	Fixes and improvements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fixes only 	Completed

NLP INTENT RECOGNITION

Module name		NLP INTENT AND SLOT RECOGNITION		
General description		This component allows interpreting user commands from text (output from speech recognition) as part of human-machine interaction.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/nlp-intent-and-slot		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Jan 2024	Demo with utterances recognized into basic commands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NLP model architecture based on BERT 	Completed
2.0	Feb 2025	Demo with utterances recognized into pilot-specific commands.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved model training Command set for KEBA pilot 	Completed
3.0	May 2025	Fixes and improvements.		Completed

3.2.8.

PERSON FOLLOWER

Module name		PERSON FOLLOWER		
General description		This component allows to detect and track a person in the collaboration ambient using the 3d camera equipped in AGVs, for the purpose of following them around.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/person-follower		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	Sep 2024	Minimal demo with recorded video.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect and track person • Display data for following person 	Completed
2.0	Dec 2024	ROS interface for integration with other modules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate using pilot-wide ROS interface 	Completed
3.0	Mar 2025	Acceleration of detection and tracking with Hailo AI.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase performance with Hailo 	Completed
4.0	Oct 2025	Rancher deployment, other fixes and improvements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only fixes 	Completed

HOOD DETECTION AND TRACKING

3 Module name				
General description		This AI-driven perception component is designed to detect and track hood components in real time. Using machine vision and deep learning algorithms, it processes camera feeds to identify hood positions and movements, enabling robots to interact dynamically with detected objects.		
Gitlab link		The link to the repository: Hood Detection and Tracking		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 2024	Initial release of the object detection module with basic tracking and position detection.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-based object tracking and processing by using video records. 	Completed
2.0	September 2024	Version with added support for multi-hood detection and tracking, handling multiple components simultaneously.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic tracking of hood components, enhanced AI capabilities, improved system scalability. 	Completed
3.0	May 2025	Enhanced version with improved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration for real-time environment 	Completed

		object tracking accuracy		
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FOLLOW ME AMR MODULE-UWB

Module name		FOLLOW ME AMR MODULE-UWB		
General description		The Follow me AMR module - UWB module detects and tracks a person in the collaborative environment using Ultra Wide Band sensor data. This technology allows collaborative robots to track a person even if there is no line of sight.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp3/ros-framework/base_hardware/uwb		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31 st , 2025	ROS2 node used to receive data from the UWB server and a launch file implementing this node with Nav2 to follow the target tag. It creates a UDP socket and publishes the filtered information received from the server.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROS2 driver for the UWB- AMR follow-me application available in repository. 	Completed

Inference Component: AI-Engine

Module name		INFERENCE COMPONENT: AI-ENGINE		
General description		Computer Vision model to detect people, forklift and dangerous areas (through geo-fencing).		
Gitlab link				
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	End of project	Computer vision model trained with public data and optimized for edge deployment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Object detection • Worker detection • Virtual geo-fencing 	Completed
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AFFECTIVE WORKER CONDITION MONITORING

Module name		AFFECTIVE WORKER CONDITION MONITORING (FORMER HEALTH STATUS MONITORING)		
General description		Components that use biometric data and context information (ocular activity, cardiovascular activity, cognitive load, task execution) to detect psychophysiological states influencing workers' conditions.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab documentation available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/reference-architecture/-/tree/main/docs/guides/Components/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/affective_worker_condition_monitoring?ref_type=heads Due to ethical and security regulations code sharing is managed internally by the responsible partner.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	30th April 2025	First release of structured biometric data (fixations, saccades, blinks, heart rate, R-R interval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First release of biometric anonymised data 	Completed
2.0 3.2.13.	End of Project	Final release of Affective Worker Condition Monitoring module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final release of the AI module calculating workers' psychophysiological states 	Completed

HUMAN STATUS ESTIMATION

Module name	
General description	This module assesses human posture and determines the worker's status by detecting abnormal behaviours. The module first receives video input of a worker collaborating with a cooperative robot. It then estimates the worker's posture from the input video and assesses the musculoskeletal risk level. Finally, it segments the entire work process

		into individual tasks, identifying frequent and abnormal patterns in task execution.		
Gitlab link	Due to company and government security regulations, code sharing via GitLab is not available. The documentation can be found in this link: https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/Components/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/human_status_estimation/			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	10th March 2025	First release of Manufacturing Worker Status Estimation module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human pose estimation from collaborative work video input • Collaborative work posture risk assessment 	Completed
2.0	End of Project	Final release of Manufacturing Worker Status Estimation module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration task segmentation from video input • Frequent and anomaly pattern detection in human pose 	Completed

3.2.14.

HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION

Module name				
General description		This AI-based module can be used to recognise human activity from video.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/human-activity-recognition		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Oct 2023	Minimal demo showing recognition of PCB handling activity of operator at KEBA.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training on video with annotated time segments 	Completed
2.0	End of Project	Final release	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only fixes 	Completed

GESTURE RECOGNITION

Module name		GESTURE RECOGNITION		
General description		This component allows to detect and recognize a hand gesture as part of human-machine interaction.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/gesture-recognition		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Oct 2025	Acceleration of detection and landmark extraction with Hailo AI.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase performance with Hailo 	Completed
2.0	Nov 2025	Minimal demo with recorded video.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformer based model for gesture classification • Detect and recognize hand gesture • Display data 	Completed
3.0	End of the project	ROS interface for integration with other modules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate using pilot-wide ROS interface 	Completed

AI-BASED AGENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – DR (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control>

COORDINATION OF AGENTS

Module name	BetFSM
General description	This module will coordinate the different agents that play a role in the execution of tasks (e.g. control, vision, planning, etc).

Gitlab link		Available at public repository https://github.com/Robotics-Research-Group-KUL/betfsm A repository with a Docker container and instructions for a small demo (to be run on a UR5e robot) is released in: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control/demo-kul		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	A finite state machine that coordinates the application. For the insertion of the PCB, it checks for the insertion states before executing the next phase so that the insertion becomes robust (e.g. first make contact with the corner, then one of the sides, etc).	Completed
2.0	30 st of September 2024	Integration of BeTFSM state machines with ROS2 eTaSL (cf. Section 3.6)	State machines for specifying the discrete state aspects of robotic skills	Completed
2.1	30 st of September 2024	Interfacing of state machines with higher level orchestration	A ROS2 action interface has been developed for Yasmin state machines	Completed
2.2	30 st of September 2024	Orchestration of application	Behaviortree.CPP action node that interfaces with the action implemented in v2.1	Completed
3.0	25 th of February 2025	Further improvement of BeTFSM including ROS2 and eTaSL integrations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python3 API • ROS2 integration for using services, topics, lifecycle state machines, etc • Action server to execute FSMs • Possibility to declare FSMs with a mix between traditional primitives and Behaviour trees primitives (e.g. sequence, concurrent, fallback, etc) 	Completed
3.1	30 th April 2025	Skill formalization using BetFSM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create re-usable skills using BetFSM and ETaSL. • Mechanisms to create libraries of skills that can be installed and easily 	Completed

			used thanks to JSON Schemas	
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BT ORCHESTRATOR

Module name		BT ORCHESTRATOR		
General description		A Behavior Tree-driven orchestrator that manages teaching, Ai-driven execution, and deviation handling workflows.		
Gitlab link		Available in private Git repositories of Profactor for the moment		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	30st of September 2024	The concept of a BT orchestrator and executor for all scenarios was developed, and initial behaviour trees were tested in the laboratory environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sharing between High Level Orchestrator blackboard and the Task executor blackboard • Robotic tasks for manipulating the laboratory Robot 	Completed
2.0	31st May 2025	Implementation and laboratory validation of the BT Orchestrator + BT Executor framework that runs PCB-testing workflows and triggers human-centered reconfiguration when a novel PCB type or grasp uncertainty occurs. The framework integrates a React GUI (workflow triggers + confirmations), multimodal teaching (geometry-based proposal → UI correction → kinesthetic teaching as fallback), and a persistent Knowledge Base for storing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BT Orchestrator / BT Executor split: orchestrator executes high-level workflows; executor handles the PCB testing subtasks and low-level errors via ROS2 actions. • Reconfiguration workflows integrated into BTs: “Generate Template” and “Generate Grasp Config” workflows, with step-wise GUI confirmations and fallback across modalities. • Multimodal grasp configuration embedded in the BT control flow: geometry proposer → UI teaching → kinesthetic teaching, with results persisted. • Knowledge Base as persistent storage (FastAPI + TinyDB) for templates, robot configs, and grasp parameters; enables reuse once a PCB is taught. 	Completed

		templates and grasp configurations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measured lab performance: full reconfiguration workflow completed in ~2.5 minutes (including operator interaction + persistence). 	
3.0	30th of November 2025	Deployment of the PROF BT Orchestrator framework at KEBA facilities with the integrated hardware/software stack used in the validated architecture: KEBA PLC hosting BT Orchestrator/Executor and ROS2 nodes, React GUI + Knowledge Base running as services, and robot/camera integration. System supports execution of the PCB testing workflow and on-the-fly reconfiguration for novel PCB variants using multimodal operator interaction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System integration on KEBA PLC + robot + UI + KB: PLC runs BT orchestrator/executor + multimodal nodes; GUI + KB run as services; communication via ROS2 + rosbridge + REST to KB. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operator-in-the-loop workflow at the pilot: GUI triggers workflows and provides confirmations; BT publishes status/events; workflow remains continuous (no "stop/reprogram/restart" loop). Reconfiguration embedded in execution: novel PCB handling through BT fallback nodes (proposal → correction), saving final config to KB for reuse. Pilot-ready benefit: reconfiguration on the order of minutes (~2.5 min end-to-end), reducing downtime compared to manual reprogramming. 	Completed
3.3.3.				

FORCE-BASED BEHAVIOURS

Module name	FORCE-BASED BEHAVIOURS
General description	Module that provides force-based behaviours for compliant execution.
Gitlab link	Publicly available and released under LGPL-V3 licence: https://github.com/Robotics-Research-Group-KUL/core_task_lib
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of June 2024	Re-usable set of constraints that can be used to create tasks that require force control (e.g. hand guiding or insertions).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admittance constraints to create different task specifications 	Completed
2.0	1 st of December 2025	Reusable constraints implemented and tested. An example can be found in <code>move_admittance.etasl.lua</code> task specification, released as part of core library of task specifications	Library released	Completed

DEPLOYABLE CONSTRAINT BASED REACTIVE CONTROL

Module name		DEPLOYABLE CONSTRAINT BASED REACTIVE CONTROL		
General description		Deployable reactive controller to execute constraint-based and sensor-based tasks programmed in eTaSL language. Some tasks can be purely modeled and some others can be learned through the PbD toolkit.		
Gitlab link		Publicly available and released under LGPL-V3 licence: https://github.com/Robotics-Research-Group-KUL/crospi		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case based on Orocos (no ROS2)	Executes learned skills for certain parts of the task (e.g. pick the pcb), and modeled skills for others (e.g. robust force-based insertion)	Completed
2.0	1 st of September 2024	Development of a ROS2 node that is independent of Orocos and can be used to execute eTaSL skills.	A highly configurable ROS2 node for task specification and execution ready.	Completed
2.1	15 th of January 2025	Increase usability by making the node easily reconfigurable through the use of JSON schemas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can reconfigure properties with Autocompletion and self-contained documentation thanks to JSON Schemas 	Completed

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic way to interface with robots via shared memory. Kuka iiwa integrated • Partial Documentation using MK Docs integrated in Gitlab pages with CI/CD. 	
2.2	5 th of March 2025	Organized template and mechanisms to create libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An application template facilitates integration of new applications • Task specification libraries can now be easily installed and reused. • JSON Schemas describing parameters of task specifications are automatically generated from the task specification file when building the application template package with colcon. 	Completed
2.3	1 st December of 2025	Augmenting usability, adding features, and completing tutorials. And release.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adding features such as new input/output handlers for other relevant msg topic types • More testing • Complete tutorials 	Completed

3.4.

AI-BASED AMBIENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – CR (UPV)

3.4.1. Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning>

REASONING MODEL

Module name	REASONING MODEL
General description	Collaboration Ambient Data Model. The Collaboration ambient data model is a data model that adds context to the data collected in the Data Platform. Based on control and enterprise systems integration standards, the model defines the production specifications (operations, materials, personnel, or equipment requirements),

	capacities, production scheduling and production performance information.			
Gitlab link	AI-PRISM data model available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aiprism-reasoning-model			
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	January 21 st 2024	This is the first version of the data model. It defines the main model structure and documentation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation about the Data Model. • Definition Model tables. • Capability Model tables. • Schedule Model tables. 	Completed
2.0	March 2024	This second version includes a first instance of the model based on AW use case.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition inserts • Schedule inserts 	Completed
3.0	September 2024	The third version provides the possibility of importing data from an Excel files.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Node-Red flow to import and structure data. • Several performance improvements 	Completed
3.1	February-March 2025	The third version of the data model went under refinements to effectively store additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated Data for Equipment Model, Personnel Model Operations definition and operations segment • Testing of the scheduling algorithm 	Completed
3.4.2. 4.0	April -May 2025	Final release	New features and fixed bugs found during the integration	Completed

HRC PAINTING RE/SCHEDULER

Module name	HRC PAINTING RE/SCHEDULER
General description	The AI-PRISM Scheduling model is a representation of all entities, their properties and the relation between them. This model allows the scheduling of the factory processes taking into consideration all available resources and restrictions, including cobots and its training requirements.
Gitlab link	Available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aw-scheduler

Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	November 31 st 2023	Gather data necessity and data output from initial design and generate an initial data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial data model for scheduling module input Initial data model for scheduling module output 	Completed
2.0	March 2024	Generate a second iteration for da data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated data model 	Completed
3.0	End of March 2024	Create a standardized version of the data model according to standard IEC62264	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardized data model 	Completed
3.0	March 2024	Service API for scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dockerized scheduling service API 	Completed
4.0	April 2025	Scheduling API tests with live data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test API Check results Update scheduling service (if necessary) 	Completed
4.5	September 2025	Scheduler API deployed in pilot. Several tests and corrections made from test deployment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final deployment of API and HRC service 	Completed

3.5.

HUMAN - MACHINE INTERACTION (HMI) MODULES – HI (KUL)

Software available here:

3.5.1.

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE

Module name	KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE
General description	The module allows the users to interact with the robot by force interaction in cartesian space at the end effector by an admittance controller. The module can be re-configured to allow changes in position, orientation, or both, and can be used with different types of robots.
Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/betfsm-gui.git https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/programming-by-demonstration-skill-library.git
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	The module allows the user to kinaesthetically guide the robot, without relying on the kinaesthetic functionalities provided by the robot manufacturer	Completed
1.1	1 st of June 2024	Demonstration of kinaesthetic teaching interface in use case inspired by KEBA pilot case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Force-based physical human interaction • Informed by the learning from demonstration to allow only variations that occur during demonstration phase 	Completed
2.0	1 st of January 2025	Backend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Facilitates mode switching	Completed
3.0	1 st of December 2025	Frontend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Allows the user to launch the kinaesthetic interaction from a GUI	Completed

3.5.2.

HRC ASSEMBLY CONSTRAINT-BASED TASKS

Module name		HRC ASSEMBLY CONSTRAINT-BASED TASKS		
General description		This module provides task specifications involving HRC in assembly		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control/force-based-assembly-task-library/		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Task specifications with hardcoded parameters to perform assembly operations with HRC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tasks (e.g. approach, make contact, etc) related to assembly applications. • Hardcoded parameters that make it hard to re-use • Implementation done in Orocos (not ROS2) 	Completed

2.0	1 st of September 2024	Task specifications with hardcoded parameters to perform assembly operations with HRC running in ROS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same task specifications as before but now running in ROS2 	Completed
3.0	15 th April 2025	Re-usable task specifications with automatically generated JSON Schemas for parameters, organized in task specification libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task specifications now are reusable and can be configured • They are organized in installable task specification libraries 	Completed

SPEECH SYNTHESIS

3	Module name	SPEECH SYNTHESIS			
	General description	This module synthesizes the robot voice for feedback as part of the voice control HMI.			
	Gitlab link	https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/speech-synthesis			
	Released versions				
	Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
	1.0	Feb 2025	Demo with voice feedback as part of voice control.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesize voice audio from text 	Completed
3.5.4.	2.0	May 2025	Fixes and improvements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only fixes 	Completed

VOICE CONTROL

Module name	VOICE CONTROL
General description	This module provides a Natural Language HMI interface to control the robot, by orchestrating the data flow from related sub-modules and implementing a natural dialog flow.

Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/voice-control		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	Feb 2025	Demo of basic voice control with voice feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestration of voice and NLP related submodules • Basic dialog flow 	Completed
2.0	May 2025	ROS interface for integration with other modules.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate using pilot-wide ROS interface 	Completed
3.0	Oct 2025	Rancher deployment, other fixes and improvements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only fixes 	Completed

SMART PICK AND PLACE FOR RECYCLING

3.5.5.

Module name		SMART PICK AND PLACE FOR RECYCLING		
General description		This AI-powered module uses advanced detection and segmentation with a stereo camera to locate bottles on a moving conveyor. A collaborative robot arm then picks and sorts the bottles, minimizing waste and improving efficiency.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	13st of February 2024	Sensor data are used to create collision models of multiple bottles to enhance performance in dynamic environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obstacle detection. • Collision models creation. 	Completed
1.1	15th of April 2024	Fine tune Open Motion Planning Library solver and add Pilz.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMPL configuration updated. • PILZ included. 	Completed

2.0	TBD	AI detection and segmentation model of bottles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial bottle detection. • Include multiple types of bottles. 	In progress
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COLLABORATIVE ORDER FORMING

Module name		COLLABORATIVE ORDER FORMING		
General description		This AI-powered module enables an Autonomous Mobile Robot (AMR) to detect, track, and follow a designated person using LIDAR data. It maintains a safe distance, avoids obstacles, and enhances warehouse picking efficiency by seamlessly assisting workers.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of February 2024	Simple human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing without tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leg detection via Random Forest on laser data. • Simple geometric leg pairing. • Simple human following for omnidirectional AMR. 	Completed
1.1	31st of May 2024	Simple human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing with Kalman tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upgraded leg detection with map masking: Significant reduction of false positives. • Advanced leg pairing using global nearest neighbours and multi-person tracking via Kalman filtering. • Simple following of locked target for any AMR 	Completed
1.2	31st of January 2025	Robust and safe human following algorithm via leg detection and pairing with Kalman tracking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust following while respecting costmap obstacles. • Safe distance form operator. • State machine and interactivity with the operator. 	Completed

SMART DEPALLETIZING

Module name		SMART DEPALLETIZING		
General description		This AI-driven module utilizes advanced detection and segmentation to dynamically locate powder sacks on loaded pallets, providing precise coordinates for a robotic suction system to efficiently pick and handle them.		
Gitlab link		Proprietary – Access granted upon agreement		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	13st of February 2024	Sensor data are used to create collision models of sacks to enhance performance in dynamic environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obstacle detection. • Collision models creation. 	Completed
1.1	15th of April 2024	Fine tune Open Motion Planning Library solver and add Pilz.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMPL configuration updated. • PILZ included. 	Completed
2.0	End of the project	AI detection and segmentation model of sacks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial sack detection. • Include multiple types of sacks. 	Completed

3.5.8.

AI ASSISTANT

Module name		AI ASSISTANT		
General description		This AI Assistant helps unskilled people operate robots with ease.		
Gitlab link		https://documentation.aiprism-srv.cigip.upv.es/guides/Components/wp4/human-robot-interaction/ai-assistant/		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31 st of June 2025	By providing clear, step-by-step instructions, it simplifies complex tasks and ensures safe, efficient operation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The assistant includes multilingual capabilities to enhance accessibility and helps operators to solve problems at the machine. 	Completed
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PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT – PD (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

3.6.

PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION TOOLKIT

Module name		PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION TOOLKIT		
General description		Toolkit to analyse demonstrations data and generate a learned motion model		
Gitlab link		For now only available in AI-PRISM repositories: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/pbd_toolkit.git		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquires demonstrations of some parts of the task and generated a learned model in a JSON format. 	Completed
1.1	31 st of sept 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific skills to demonstrate the picking and placing of PCB's 	Completed
2.0	15 th of May 2025	Preliminary toolkit version for processing demonstrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Python implementation to process set of demonstrations Configurable parameters to adapt to learning situation 	Completed
2.1	15 th of July 2025	Toolkit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Backend implementation to easily record and process demonstrations Visualization tools to help to analyze the generated motion model 	Completed

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kinematic simulation facilities to test with a virtual robot. 	
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PAINTING PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION

Module name		PAINTING PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION		
General description		The module allows the users to interact with the robot in a virtual reality environment. It allows to control the painting robot remotely or to teach how to paint new pieces of furniture.		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction/programming-by-demonstration-with-vr		
Released versions		2		
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Preliminary demonstrator for internal review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control the robot in virtual reality. • Control a UR robot using TCP sockets 	Completed
2.0	December 2024	ROS 2 compatibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration with ROS 2 driver. • Integration with other WP4 components (reasoning model and cluster management). 	Completed
3.0	December 2025	Final version	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New features and bug fixes identified during tests 	Completed

3.6.3.

MULTIMODAL INTERFACES

Module name		MULTIMODAL INTERFACES		
General description		This module on multi-modal interfaces—integrates GUI, kinaesthetic, and vision-based interactions—enhances robot task programming by enabling intuitive, adaptive, and user-friendly interaction, facilitating seamless human-robot collaboration in dynamic industrial environments.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repositories. AI-PRISM / WP6 - Pilots / KEBA / ai_prism_multi_modal_frontend_docker · GitLab		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	31st of March 2024	This module Utilizes hand-guiding mode for human-driven configuration the PCB picking task. Key processes include template creation, transformation calculations, and related tasks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prototype-level development • PCB picking configuration utilizing Kinesthetic Teaching • Configuration Template generation • Transformation and alignment calculations 	Completed
2.0	30st of September 2024	Vision-based system for teaching and correcting PCB pose prior to placement. The system is utilized after the human-assisted PCB picking configuration step. It uses sensor fusion combining low-cost and industrial-grade imaging solutions. The process includes PCB alignment into the focus plane of the camera.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vision-based PCB pose teaching • Sensor fusion (low-cost + industrial cameras) • PCB alignment into focus plane 	Completed
3.0	31st of March 2025	Simple User Interface for grasping point teaching, enhanced with AI that suggests efficient grasping points for novel PCB Types, with algorithms that consider end-effector geometries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intuitive grasp point teaching utilizing GUI • AI-based grasp point suggestion • Algorithms account for specific end-effector geometries 	Completed
4.0	31st of May 2025	An intuitive react GUI serves the operator with various teaching modalities, allowing individual selection based on individual preferences. Additionally, a configuration wizard enables workers on the shopfloor to create new PCB configurations directly.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intuitive GUI for operator interaction • Multiple selectable teaching modalities • Configuration wizard for creating new PCB configurations for novel PCB types. • Target Operator: non robotic expert. 	Completed

SKILLS FOR COMPLEX TASKS

Module name		SKILLS FOR COMPLEX TASKS		
General description		Skills for complex tasks that require force-based robot behaviors (e.g. insertion) or learning from demonstrations		
Gitlab link		https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control/force-based-assembly-and-learning-from-demonstration-skill-library.git		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Examples of skills for complex tasks such as insertions in Orocos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through a collection of task specifications and coordination with rFSM in Orocos. • Hardcoded parameters which make the skill difficult to reuse 	Completed
2.0	31 st of sept 2024	Examples of skills for complex tasks such as insertions in ROS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through a collection of task specifications and coordination with BeTFsm in ROS2. • Hardcoded parameters which make the skill difficult to reuse 	Completed
3.0	15 th of May 2025	Re-usable skill libraries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented through tasks coming from task specification libraries and coordination with BetFSM in ROS2. • Reconfigurable through parameters with JSON Schemas • Organized in re-usable skill libraries 	Completed

4. Conclusions

SUMMARY

The report describes the software versions and their status in a tabular manner, containing high-level information of the consecutive releases of the CI/CD framework and AI-based enhancing modules designed to enhance the perception and reasoning capabilities of robotic agents within the collaborative environment. The document contains the details and status of the components developed from months 7 to 39. The high-level description of each module describes its purpose in the project and project pilot, links to software and documentation, and the status and features of its consecutive released versions. Together, this deliverable and its companion D3.4. document the status of all software components developed in AI-PRISM.

FINAL REMARKS

D4.4 is the final deliverable documenting the software components of the project. No further versions of this document are planned. This report consolidates all relevant information on the developed modules and their releases, providing a complete overview of the software status at the end of the project.